

Deliverable 3.2: Courses for early stage researchers

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
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Nature	R (Document, report - excluding the periodic and final reports)
Dissemination level	PU (Public, fully open, e.g. web)

Executive summary

Training courses were organised by the coordinator in collaboration with the consortium partners NILU and FhG for early stage researchers to acquire new skills and knowledge in the fields of scientific writing, interacting with industry, proposal writing and project management. Four courses in the fields mentioned above were realized until now.

The training courses were organized as open call events for all students, not limited for students at BMC SAV in Slovakia.

1 Description of work & main achievements

1.1 Training courses for acquiring and expanding skills of early stage researchers

To give students the opportunity to acquire new skills or expand their skills of early stage researchers, the coordinator, in collaboration with the consortium partners NILU and FhG, organized training courses in the fields of interacting with industry, scientific writing, project management and proposal writing.

The following four courses were realized in September 2020 as webinars. Information about the number of participants and the organizers as well as the specific day of the events is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of already organized courses

Date	Topic of the course	Course given by	Number of attendees
10.09.2020	How to interact with industry	FhG	22
11.09.2020	Academic publishing	FhG	29
16.09.2020	Project management	NILU	30
17.09.-18.9.2020	How to write proposals	NILU	37

The training courses were organized as open call events for all interested students, not limited for students at BMC SAV in Slovakia. The invitation for the courses was published on the VISION website and Facebook. The information on courses was also disseminated by partners.

For each training course a certificate of attendance, signed by the coordinator and the respective lecturers, were handed out to each participant.

It was jointly decided that the courses will be repeated in 2021 and 2022.

1.1.1 Course 1 "How to interact with industry"

Fraunhofer is the international leader of applied research. Part I of the course introduced the Fraunhofer Society, from history to research fields and cooperation models. Examples of successful collaborations with industry were presented. Part II focused on the Fraunhofer IBMT, with examples of collaborations with industry in the field of biology and medicine. Part III gave an overview of national and international funding opportunities for projects with industry.

1.1.2 Course 2 "Academic publishing"

Academic publishing includes master thesis writing, PhD thesis writing, research paper writing, scientific poster and oral presentation. For all this publishing types scientific writing is essential. Thus this course introduced to effective writing, formatting, organization of a scientific writing process, the publication process. Besides theory, the presentations included tips and a lot of

examples. Also the aspects of citation and plagiarism, authorship were discussed. Part III of the course included an exercise on finding the right journal for publishing your data.

1.1.3 Course 3 "Project management"

This training course dealt with the following topics: Implementation, impact, consortium, management and resources, administrative and formal issues, intellectual properties rights, and patent applications.

1.1.4 Course 4 "How to write proposals"

NILU has great experience in writing proposals and success in obtaining EC grants. During the course NILU shared this experience. Theoretical and practical training how to write proposals with focus on highly innovative objectives excellence and feasible work plan were part of the training.

2 Deviation from the workplan

There are no deviations from the work plan.

3 Conclusion

Four training courses were successfully implemented between 10.09.2020 and 18.09.2020. The number of participants per course was between 22 and 37 persons. Certificates of attendance, signed by the coordinator and the respective lecturers, were handed out to each participant. The courses will be repeated in 2021 and 2022. The selected materials from these courses are available on the project website.